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ANALYSIS OF POPULATION DYNAMICS
IN SPECIES WITH CONTINUOUS RECRUITMENT
AND UNOBSERVABLE AGE STRUCTURE

Abstract

An analysis of the literature concerning the methods for the estimation of birth and death rates for populations with continuous recruitment and unobservable age structure is presented from a critical point of view. Some new ideas and mathematical formulations are introduced.

Finally an evaluation of possible approximations based on extension of the classical mathematical demography is presented and discussed.

1. INTRODUCTION.

An important problem in population dynamics is that of birth and death rates estimation. A proper estimate of these rates is of great importance in order to understand the mechanisms of population control. Unfortunately for many species of large ecological significance, such as zooplanktonic crustacea and polivoltine insects, the demographic and reproductive features of the population are very complex. In fact, common is the case of populations with continuous recruitment and unobservable age structure. These populations usually play an important role in the community so that a proper estimation of the birth and death rates for this difficult case could be of crucial importance.

The considerable effort devoted to this problem in the past 20 years (Edmondson, 1960, 1968; Caswell, 1972; Pelloheimo, 1974; Argentesi, de Bernardi and Di Cola, 1974; Threlkeld, 1979; Seitz, 1979) has been based on assumptions about the form of the age structure. These assumptions were mainly of two types: uniform or exponential age distribution for the whole population or, when the case, for the considered developmental stages. Starting from this basis, various, more

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or less complex models have been proposed in order to describe the population dynamics and therefore to estimate the birth and death rates.

A brief review of these models is presented in the section 5 of this paper by reconstructing conceptually the various estimation methods of the literature. In sections 2 to 3, we look at the problem from the classical mathematical demography point of view.

In this way, the empirical models of section 4 can be compared with the classical formulation (exponential age structure).

The contribution of the present study to this field is introduced in section 5 and developed in section 6, where a method, based on time-lag models for birth and death rates estimation not assuming but reconstructing age structure, is presented and examined in some detail.

Future perspectives are introduced focusing on the mathematical and numerical problems associated with the use of these time-lag models.

2. THE VON FOERSTER EQUATION AND THE SHARPE-LOTKA MODEL FOR ONE-SEX POPULATIONS.

As a basic formal assessment of our population dynamics problem, we will refer to the Von Foerster equation (Von Foerster, 1959) where the population process is described in continuous age and time. This equation is given by:

$$\frac{\partial n(a, t)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial n(a, t)}{\partial a} = -\mu(a, t) n(a, t) \quad (1)$$

with the associated initial and boundary conditions:

$$n(a, 0) = \varphi_0(a) \quad (2)$$

and

$$n(0, t) = \int_0^{\infty} \lambda(a', t) n(a', t) da' \quad (3)$$

This latter equation, known as renewal equation, is of primary importance in demography. For more details about the Von Foerster equation and its derivation see Argentesi, de Bernardi and Di Cola (1974). The continuous-time model, proposed seventy years ago by Sharpe and Lotka (Sharpe and Lotka, 1911) for the estimation of the intrinsic growth rate of human population, is a formulation under

proper conditions of the renewal equation (3).

The model is a one-sex model and applies to female populations only. However, the extension to a two sexes population does not present particular difficulties when the sex ratio is introduced in (3). We define $n(a, t) da$ to be the number of females at time t whose ages lie between a and $a + da$; $B(t) dt$ to be the number of female births during the time element $(t, t + dt)$; μ and λ are the unity mortality and fecundity rates respectively.

The initial condition is given by the function $\phi_0(a)$ which provide the number of individuals of age a at time 0.

We assume $\lambda(a, t)$ and $\mu(a, t)$ as time independent (this assumption may be acceptable under the limited environmental variations that usually occur in short intervals of time).

From these definitions it follows:

$$n(a, t) = B(t-a) s(a) \quad (0 \leq a \leq t) \quad (4)$$

and

$$n(a, t) = \phi_0(a-t) [s(a)/s(a-t)] \quad (a > t)$$

The survival rate $s(a)$ is related to the mortality rate $\mu(a)$ by the equation:

$$\frac{ds(a)}{da} + s(a) \mu(a) = 0$$

Moreover the renewal equation (3) becomes:

$$B(t) = \int_0^{\infty} n(a, t) \lambda(a) da \quad (5)$$

From (5) it follows:

$$B(t) = \int_0^t B(t-a) s(a) \lambda(a) da + G(t) \quad (6)$$

where

$$G(t) = \int_t^{\infty} \phi_0(a-t) \lambda(a) s(a)/s(a-t) da$$

For large values of t , ($t \gg a$), $G(t)$ can be neglected and equation (6) becomes:

$$B(t) \cong \int_0^t B(t-a) \lambda(a) s(a) da \quad (7)$$

This equation is the Lotka equation.

Under the hypothesis of stationary exponential growth (constant λ and μ) of the population, the age structure can be simply derived.

There is a limiting case of exponential growth when $r = 0$ (r being the unity intrinsic rate of growth of the population): this means that the population is in a stationary phase and that the age distribution is uniform.

3. POPULATIONS REPRESENTATION BY DEVELOPMENTAL STAGES.

As already remarked in the introduction, many populations with continuous recruitment do not permit any experimental observation of the age structure, while, when the populations age structure is known, the estimation of the birth and death rates are straightforward.

If the age structure is not observable, as we will see, the evaluation of the population dynamics parameters seems to be possible only under rough approximations. In any case, some aspects of the age structure can be accounted for by taking advantage of the species life history.

The subdivision in developmental stages such as eggs, youngs, adults, or even more detailed, is a fairly old practice for the population biologists. The use of this methodology can be of advantage in the relieve of some of the strong hypotheses of the previous section. We will consider, for example, a two-stage model related to eggs and adults only. We assume $\lambda, \mu = \text{constant}$. In this case we have:

$$\begin{aligned} E(t) &= \int_0^{D_E} n_E(a, t) da && \text{eggs stage} \\ N(t) &= \int_0^{\infty} n_N(a, t) da && \text{adults stage} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where $E(t)$ and $N(t)$ are the number of eggs and adults observable in the population at time t , and D_E is the development time of the eggs. In other terms we consider:

$$\begin{aligned} n_E(x, t) & \quad 0 \leq x \leq D_E && \text{as the age components of the eggs, and} \\ n_N(x, t) & \quad 0 \leq x && \text{as the age components of the adults;} \end{aligned}$$

x refers to the ages within the stages, the interface condition being:

$$n_E(D_E, t) = n_N(0, t)$$

The continuity equations can be easily derived by analogy with the Von Foerster equation:

$$\frac{\partial n_E(x, t)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial n_E(x, t)}{\partial x} = \mu_E n_E(x, t), \quad 0 \leq x \leq D_E$$

$$\frac{\partial n_N(x, t)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial n_N(x, t)}{\partial x} = \mu_N n_N(x, t), \quad 0 \leq x < \infty$$
(9)

where μ_E and μ_N are the instantaneous mortality rates for eggs and adults respectively.

The renewal equation will be:

$$n_E(0, t) = \int_0^{\infty} \lambda n_N(x, t) dx$$
(10)

λ , μ_E and μ_N being assumed constants and age independent.

By integrating over the ages, the continuity equations can be rewritten as follows:

$$\frac{dE(t)}{dt} = \lambda N(t) - \lambda N(t - D_E) e^{-\mu_E D_E} - \mu_E E(t) \quad \text{for } D_E < t$$

$$\frac{dN(t)}{dt} = \lambda N(t - D_E) e^{-\mu_E D_E} - \mu_N N(t) \quad \text{for } D_E < t$$
(11)

The transfer rate models assumed in Argentesi, de Bernardi and Di Cola (1974), on the basis of Emondson (1960) formulations as E/D_E , are the counterpart of the transfer rate

$$\lambda N(t - D_E) e^{-\mu_E D_E} \quad \text{of equation (11).}$$

In addition, it must be noticed that equation (11) reduces to the time-lag equation introduced in Argentesi, de Bernardi and Di Cola (1974) by taking $\mu_E = 0$.

On the basis of the renewal equation, a convenient integral formulation for $E(t)$ and $N(t)$ can be derived.

In fact we have:

$$E(t) = \lambda \int_0^{D_E} N(t-x) e^{-\mu_E x} dx, \quad t > D_E$$
(12)

$$N(t) = \lambda \int_0^{t-D_E} N(t-D_E-x) e^{-\mu_N x} e^{-\mu_E D_E} dx, \quad t > D_E$$
(13)

A relieve of the strong restrictions previously imposed ($\mu(x) = \mu = \text{const.}$) is possible. Consequently equations (12) and (13) become:

$$E(t) = \int_0^{D_1} N(t-x) \lambda_{SE}(x) dx \quad (14)$$

where $s_E(x)$ is the solution of the differential equation

$$\frac{ds_E(x)}{dx} + \mu_E(x) \cdot s_E(x) = 0$$

In addition

$$N(t) = \int_0^{t-D_1} N(t-D_E-x) \lambda_{SE}(D_E) s_N(x) dx \quad (15)$$

where $s_N(x)$ is the solution of the differential equation

$$\frac{ds_N(x)}{dx} + \mu_N(x) s_N(x) = 0$$

It appears clear that it is easy to extend equations (9), (10), (11), (12), (13), (14) and (15) to three or more stages.

3.1 Models with more than two stages

Starting from the Von Foerster equation, the authors (Argentesi, de Bernardi and Di Cola, 1974) derived a large class of models and their estimators for fecundity, birth and stage specific death rates.

As a first step, these models were formulated in an open way, i.e. the transfer rates modelling was left open for various possible formulations. On the basis of specific assumptions, about the age structure of the natural zooplanktonic populations, developed in the part of the paper concerning applications, the uniform age distribution was taken and the transfer between stages $R_x(t)$ represented by N_x/D_x . Deriving the model by discretization of the Von Foerster equation, the system can be written as follows:

$$\frac{dN_i(t)}{dt} = R_i(t) - R_{i+1}(t) - \mu_i(t) N_i(t) \quad (16)$$

with

$$R_0 = \sum_{i=0}^K \lambda_i(t) N_i(t)$$

being the discrete counterpart of the renewal equation.

It can be assumed that:

$$R_{i+1}(t) = R_i(t - D_i) s_i(t)$$

where $s_i(t)$ is the finite survival rate of the individuals in age class i , that means that the recruited individuals in the $i + 1$ class are equal to the recruited individuals of the class i at time $t - D_i$ and survived at time t .

In the particular case where $\mu_i(t) = \text{const.}$ we have:

$$s_i(t) = e^{-\mu_i D_i}$$

Equation (16) becomes:

$$\frac{dN_i(t)}{dt} = R_i(t) - R_i(t - D_i) s_i(t) - \mu_i(t) N_i(t) \tag{17}$$

The equation (17) for $i = 0$ is:

$$\frac{dN_0(t)}{dt} = R_0(t) - R_0(t - D_0) s_0(t) - \mu_0(t) N_0(t) \tag{17a}$$

In order to have a simplified representation, we assume that, among the K stages, only N_K is producing eggs (this limitation is not strictly necessary), that is $N_0 = \lambda(t) N_K(t)$.

In addition, assuming λ and μ as time independent and by using the renewal equation, we can derive integral equations equivalent to (17), that represent a generalization of equation (12) and (13). In fact we can write:

$$N_i(t) = \lambda \int_0^{D_i} e^{-\mu x} N_K(t - x - \sum_{J=0}^{i-1} D_J) e^{-\sum_{J=0}^i \mu_J D_J} dx \tag{18}$$

$$t > \sum_{J=0}^i D_J$$

and

$$N_K(t) = \lambda \int_0^{t - \sum_{J=0}^{K-1} D_J} e^{-\mu_K x} N_K(t - x - \sum_{J=0}^{K-1} D_J) e^{-\sum_{J=0}^{K-1} \mu_J D_J} dx \tag{18a}$$

$$t > \sum_{J=0}^{K-1} D_J$$

The parameter estimation problem on the basis of equations (18a) is not a simple problem and it requires proper numerical methods. We can formulate this problem as follows.

Let be:

$$J = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{l=0}^K W_l (N_i(t_l) - \bar{N}_i(t_l))^2$$

a measure of distance between observed and predicted population densities. The $\bar{N}_i(t_l)$ are the observations of the number of animals in the $\bar{N}_i$ development stage at time t_l , W_l are weights functions and $N_i(t_l)$ are the corresponding predicted values.

The estimation problem can be solved by minimizing the functional J under the constraints of the integral equation (18a) or alternatively under the differential constraints (17).

The solution of this estimation problem requires complex mathematical and numerical tools because these inverse problems are usually ill posed. These difficulties could be overcome by introducing proper smoothing conditions.

4. EMPIRICAL MODELS FOR THE ESTIMATION OF THE POPULATION PROCESS PARAMETERS.

In the previous paragraphs the representation by developmental stages of birth and death rates estimation has been derived from the classical demography models. This estimation problem is difficult because only the counts for $E(t)$ and $N(t)$ (in the two stage case) and the measure of D_E at specific times t_i , $i = 1 \dots M$, are usually available for the natural populations.

Starting from this experimental information and making a series of further hypotheses on the properties of the population dynamics, several estimation methods have been proposed in the last 20 years, in order to estimate unity birth and death rates.

In the following subsections, we will present a short analysis of the most relevant contributions to the solution of this problem. As we will see, the methods considered here below are derived on empirical assumptions rather than on the mathematical demography formulations available.

For this reason, we call them empirical methods.

Edmondson (1960)

One of the first attempts to estimate the birth and death rates

was made by Edmondson (1960). In his paper, Edmondson makes the following assumptions:

- 1) the population is in a stationary exponential growth in the interval $(t, t+1)$ considered (the time scale is arbitrary);
- 2) the observations provide $E_t, E_{t+1}, N_t, N_{t+1}$ and D_E for the interval. Edmondson gives two models, one (M1) for the number of births in the interval $(t, t+1)$ given by:

$$\frac{E_t}{D_E} = \int_t^{t+1} bN_\tau d\tau \quad (\text{M1})$$

where b is the unitary birth rate and N_τ the number of adults at time τ ; the other (M2) for the population density behaviour in the same interval of time, e.g. the exponential growth:

$$N_\tau = N_t e^{r(\tau-t)} \quad (\text{M2})$$

where r is the intrinsic unity growth rate.

It has to be noticed that Edmondson uses the model (M2) with $\tau = t+1$

$$N_{t+1} = N_t e^r$$

and he estimates r as follows:

$$r = \ln \frac{N_{t+1}}{N_t}$$

Moreover he assumes:

$$r = b - \mu$$

where μ is the unitary death rate of the population. Despite of this adequate formulation of the exponential growth, he takes in the computation of b by models (M1) and (M2):

$$r = b \quad \text{and} \quad \mu = 0$$

The introduction of E_t/D_E in model (M1) based on an assumption of Elster (1954) is unusual in mathematical demography, but of common use in the description of important physical and chemical processes (e.g. radioactive decay). Model (M1) requires a uniform age structure for the eggs population. This uniform age structure

is coherent with the stationary exponential growth only if $r = 0$, i.e. only if the population does not grow in the interval.

The analogy with the decay models permits the interpretation of E_t/D_E as instantaneous birth rate ($dE/dt = -(1/D_E)E$) (this representation is at the basis of the differential equations model given by Argentesi, de Bernardi and Di Cola (1974)).

Nevertheless, Elster (1954) and Edmondson (1960) assumed $1/D_E$ as a finite unitary birth rate. This gives rise to significant differences between the Argentesi, de Bernardi and Di Cola (1974) and the Edmondson (1960) models. Edmondson derives the instantaneous birth rate as follows:

$$\frac{E_t}{D_E} = \int_t^{t+1} bN_\tau d\tau \quad (19)$$

and assuming the exponential model

$$N_\tau = N_t e^{b(\tau-t)}$$

he obtains the following results:

$$\frac{E_t}{D_E} = bN_t \int_t^{t+1} e^{b(\tau-t)} d\tau = N_t(e^b - 1) \quad (20)$$

or in other terms

$$B = \frac{E_t}{D_E N_t} = e^b - 1$$

In this estimation there are three main assumptions: no eggs and adults mortality, representation of the births in the interval with a model not properly representing the real exponential growth. In the case where:

$$B \ll 1 \quad \ln(1 + B) \cong B$$

it follows that

$$b \cong \frac{E_t}{D_E N_t}$$

Caswell (1972)

Caswell (1972) in a rather concise paper (no precise model is formulated for the number of births in the interval, but E_t/D_E is used implicitly) provides an estimation which introduces the adults mortality in M2 model.

The Caswell formula for b can be derived by simple substitution of M2 into M1.

$$\frac{E_t}{D_E} = b N_t \int_t^{t+1} e^{r(\tau-t)} d\tau = \frac{b}{r} N_t (e^r - 1) \quad (21)$$

then

$$b = \frac{E_t}{D_E N_t} \cdot \frac{r}{e^r - 1}$$

The estimation of r is made as in Edmondson. This estimator of b does not remove the incoherences of the uniform age structure and of the no eggs mortality.

Paloheimo (1974)

With Paloheimo (1974) there is in some extent a return to the formulations of the classical mathematical demography. In fact, the Paloheimo estimator is an approximation of the classical demography estimation. In order to show this strict connection, we will derive the Paloheimo formula from equations (12) and (13). The eggs-females ratio can be given as:

$$\frac{E(t)}{N(t)} = \frac{\lambda \int_0^{D_E} N(t-x) e^{-\mu x} dx}{\lambda \int_0^{t-D_E} N(t-x-D_E) e^{-\mu D_E} e^{-\mu x} dx}$$

There is the usual assumption of exponential growth, exponential stable age structure and the further assumption of $\mu_E = \mu_N = \mu$. This latter assumption is reasonable for example for Cladocera populations. Moreover, it is assumed that (as in Edmondson, 1960) $r = b - \mu$ where b is the unitary birth rate. It must be noticed that λ in the

classical demography representation of the eggs-females' ratio is the unitary fecundity rate. Making the usual substitutions, we have:

$$\frac{E(t)}{N(t)} = \frac{\int_0^{D_E} e^{-rx} e^{-\mu x} dx}{\int_0^{t-D_E} e^{-r(x+D_E)} e^{-\mu(x+D_E)} dx}$$

$$\frac{E(t)}{N(t)} = e^{bD_E} \frac{1 - e^{-bD_E}}{1 - e^{-(t-D_E)}} \quad (22)$$

$$\frac{E(t)}{N(t)} = b \frac{e^{bD_E} - 1}{1 - e^{-bD_E} e^{-bt}}$$

Equation (22) is in fact a typical derivation from the classical demography representation of the eggs-females ratio.

If t is sufficiently large, equation (22) gives rise to the Paloheimo equation, i.e. e^{-bt} is going to zero if b is not too small and t is sufficiently large. Under these conditions we have:

$$\frac{E(t)}{N(t)} = e^{bD_E} - 1 \quad (23)$$

If we put:

$$F = \frac{E(t)}{N(t)}$$

$$b = \frac{\ln(1 + F)}{D_E} \quad (24)$$

which is the Paloheimo (1974) estimator.

A similar formula was also derived by Edmondson (1968). In some cases the use of equation (23) instead of equation (22) could give rise to very different estimates for b . If:

$$F \ll 1 \quad \ln(1 + F) \cong F$$

then

$$b \cong \frac{E_t}{D_E N_t}$$

5. NATURAL POPULATIONS AND AGE STRUCTURE.

The study of natural populations of zooplanktonic species is of course hardly reducible to either the assumptions of classical demography or to the empirical idea of uniform age structure for the various development stages. Phenomena like age specific predation and competition may create situations called « catastrophic events » in classical demography. These « catastrophic events » violate deeply the assumptions of stationary exponential growth and normal age structure, even if we consider short time intervals.

It is our opinion that for what concerns zooplanktonic natural populations, the assumptions of the classical demography are misleading and can create the illusion of being able to solve the problem. In fact, in field conditions, we can say that the age structure is rapidly changing (Threlkeld, 1979) and it is unobservable.

Strong hypotheses about this structure are of course possible but we believe that the hypothesis of the type: fixed exponential or uniform cannot be of real practical utility for natural populations.

Disputes about one or the other could be misleading and give little contribution to the solution of the problem. In fact, our estimation problem is a puzzling problem indeed. The real age structures of the development stages in which the population has been subdivided are not observable and probably are complex and rapidly changing with time. The usual age structures hypotheses are too simple in order to be able of providing unbiased and consistent estimate of the population dynamic parameters.

At the present stage of development of this field, the only approach that seems capable of giving an answer to our estimation problem is that of the time-delay models that at least in principle could reconstruct the age structure.

6. AGE STRUCTURE RECONSTRUCTION AND TIME-DELAY DIFFERENTIAL EQUATION MODELS.

In our paper of 1974 (Argentesi, de Bernardi and Di Cola, 1974) a simple version of a two-stage time-delay model was introduced under the simple hypothesis of no eggs mortality.

In order to avoid assumptions about the age structure of the eggs, we can formulate the following model:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dE(t)}{dt} &= R_0 - R_1 - \mu_E(t) E(t) \\ \frac{dN(t)}{dt} &= R_1 - \mu_N(t) N(t) \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

with

$$R_0 = \lambda(t) N(t)$$

$$R_1 = \lambda(t - D_E) N(t - D_E) e^{-\int_0^{D_E} \mu_E(t-\tau) d\tau}$$

It must be noticed that the fecundity rate $\lambda(t)$ is now time variable as the two mortality rates $\mu_E(t)$ and $\mu_N(t)$. Equation (25) can be directly derived from equations (17) under the hypothesis:

$$s_E(t) = e^{-\int_0^{D_E} \mu_E(t-\tau) d\tau}$$

If we assume, as in Argentesi, de Bernardi and Di Cola, (1974) that $\dot{E}(t) = dE(t)/dt$, $\dot{N}(t) = dN(t)/dt$; $N(t)$, $E(t)$ and D_E are observable or numerically estimable from the data, it is possible to design an estimator for $\lambda(t)$ and $\mu_E(t) = \mu_N(t) = \mu(t)$. This estimator can be operated only for $t \gg D_E$ and it requires the knowledge of $\lambda(t)$, $\mu(t)$ and $N(t)$ for $0 \leq t \leq D_E$.

In fact we can write:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{E}(t) = \lambda(t)N(t) - \lambda(t - D_E)N(t - D_E) e^{-\int_0^{D_E} \mu(t-\tau) d\tau} - \mu(t)E(t) \\ \dot{N}(t) = \lambda(t - D_E)N(t - D_E) e^{-\int_0^{D_E} \mu(t-\tau) d\tau} - \mu(t)N(t) \end{cases} \quad (25a)$$

Let $N(t)$, $\lambda(t)$ and $\mu(t)$ already known for $t \leq D_E$. At time $t > D_E$ the following term is known:

$$\lambda(t - D_E)N(t - D_E) e^{-\int_0^{D_E} \mu(t-\tau) d\tau} = \alpha(t)$$

Therefore we have:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{E}(t) = \lambda(t) N(t) - \alpha(t) - \mu(t) E(t) \\ \dot{N}(t) = \alpha(t) - \mu(t) N(t) \end{cases} \quad (25b)$$

and

$$\begin{cases} \mu(t) = (\alpha(t) - \dot{N}(t))/N(t) \\ \lambda(t) = (\dot{E}(t) + \alpha(t) + \mu(t))/E(t) \end{cases} \quad (26)$$

The basic difficulty here is the availability of an unbiased estimate of $\lambda(t)$ and $\mu(t)$ for $0 \leq t \leq D_E$ and the numerical stability of equations (26) when dealing with data affected by errors. Estimator (26) does not make any assumption of a known and stable age structure since it reconstructs at each time the eggs age structure.

The practical use of estimators of the type of equations (26) is difficult because it is not easy to have unbiased estimates of $\lambda(t)$ and $\mu(t)$ for $0 \leq t \leq D_E$. Moreover, the numerical stability of (26), as shown by simulation studies, could be not very high.

7. CONCLUSION.

Apart from this class of time-delay models, it seems impossible until now to achieve a credible approach to fecundity, birth and death rates estimation in natural populations with unobservable and time variable age structure. Of course, in some cases, simple models for the birth process such as in Paloheimo (1974) or in Argentesi, de Bernardi and Di Cola (1974), could be of practical utility.

In fact if the population grow exponentially for long periods of time (i.e.: the age structure can be approximated by a stationary exponential) the Paloheimo's model could give reasonable approximation of the unitary birth rate.

When the population is in a stationary state (i.e. the total growth rate is zero) the age distribution is uniform for both eggs and other developmental stages.

In this case the Argentesi, de Bernardi and Di Cola (1974) model provide a good estimate of the unitary birth and fecundity rates.

The technical difficulties for the use of the time-lag models with field data are certainly notable. The convergence of the estimator (26) starting from biased estimated of $\lambda(t)$ and $\mu(t)$ must be studied in details. Moreover the numerical stability of specific implementations of estimators of the type given by equation (26) requires careful analysis.

We started recently some systematic studies on this subject. Preliminary results seem to support an optimistic view on the practical utilization of the time-lag models in the birth and death rates estimation in natural zooplanktonic populations.

SUMMARY.

In recent years a considerable amount of research effort has been devoted to the problem of the estimation of birth and death rates in natural zooplanktonic populations. This problem is complex and unfortunately neither the classical methods of mathematical demography nor the sometimes naive introduction of empirical models are able to provide solutions of general applicability in the field. The most puzzling aspects of this problem are due to the unstable and unobservable age structure of these populations.

In this paper we will present a critical review of the proposed formulations for birth and death rates estimation in zooplanktonic populations. Moreover some ideas concerning the assessment of the most important approaches are given in some detail.

Few basic lines for a solution of this remarkable problem of zooplankton population dynamics are introduced as an extension of a class of models presented in a previous paper.

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